

Thermoacoustic properties of lysine hydrochloride in aqueous and in mixed aqueous solutions

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Abstract : Density, ultrasonic velocity, apparent molal volume, apparent molal adiabatic compressibility, relative association and viscosity of lysine hydrochloride has been determined in water and in mixed aqueous solutions of tetrahydrofuran at 300.56 K. The data has been used to calculate limiting apparent molal volume, limiting apparent adiabatic compressibility, the corresponding constants S_v and S_k . The viscosity coefficients have been calculated using Jones-Dole equation. These quantities have been discussed in the light of intermolecular interactions.

Keywords : Intermolecular interactions, ultrasonic velocity, apparent molal volume, apparent molal adiabatic compressibility.

Introduction

Compressibility of liquids is an essential physical characteristic which reflects intermolecular interactions and dynamic processes occurring in solutions. The experimental data in compressibility of liquids is analyzed in terms of solute-solvent/solution interactions and thereby developing the empirical structural-compressibility relationship¹. In this paper, we present the thermodynamic studies of lysine hydrochloride in aqueous and in mixed aqueous solutions. The water and tetrahydrofuran (THF) has proved to be most interesting solution due to hydrogen bond interaction of water with THF². Additionally, THF is used as solvent in many pharmaceutical and synthetic procedures due to its broad solvacy for polar and non-polar compounds³. As one of the most polar cyclic ethers it is a useful solvent, much less potent anesthetic and more ecologically friendly than diethyl ether. Moreover, a literature survey indicates that no physico-chemical study on this system has been reported using THF as solvent. Thus an attempt has been made to understand the behaviour of lysine hydrochloride with water and water/THF mixed solution at 300.56 K using ultrasonic velocity measurements.

Theory, Results and discussion

The adiabatic compressibility (K_s) of solution is expressed as :

$$K_s = 1/u^2d$$

where u is the ultrasonic velocity and d is the density of the solution.

A perusal of Table 1 (only selected concentrations are displayed in the Table) shows that the density increases with the increase in molality of lysine hydrochloride in aqueous solution as well as with different concentrations of aqueous THF. However, the density of solution (water + THF), referred now as solvent, decreases as the concentration of solvent is increased. The increase in the value of density may be attributed to the increase in hydrophilic interactions. The table also reveals that the ultrasonic velocity increases both with the increase in molality of lysine hydrochloride as well as increase in the concentration of aqueous THF. Simultaneously, the value of adiabatic compressibility decreases. However, the situation reverses when the concentration of aqueous THF exceeds beyond 25%. The studies show that when the concentration of mixed aqueous solution becomes greater than 28%, the ultrasonic velocity decreases while adiabatic compressibility increases nearly in the same range of molality. The increase or decrease in ultrasonic velocity depends on the structure properties of solute⁴. The cohesion brought about by ionic hydration is responsible for rising trend in the ultrasonic velocity. When the compound is dissolved in solvent (water and THF), the posi-

Table 1. Molalities, densities, ultrasonic velocities, compressibilities, apparent molal volumes, apparent molal adiabatic compressibilities and relative association of lysine hydrochloride at 300.56 K in water and in mixed aqueous solutions of THF

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	d (kg m ⁻³)	u (m s ⁻¹)	$K_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	$\Phi_v \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Phi_k \times 10^{15}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	R_A
Lysine HCl in aqueous solution						
0.00000	996.4059	1500.86	4.46			
0.09994	1003.3657	1515.39	4.34	112.381	-67.1	1.00376
0.19999	1009.1018	1528.80	4.24	117.866	-58.1	1.00653
0.29997	1014.2318	1541.37	4.15	121.284	-51.8	1.00889
0.39997	1018.3952	1555.17	4.06	125.172	-48.4	1.01003
Lysine HCl in 10% aqueous THF						
0.00000	993.2763	1555.20	4.16			
0.09994	999.3751	1562.23	4.10	121.288	-13.3	1.00463
0.19996	1005.0337	1571.29	4.03	122.835	-17.2	1.00837
0.29990	1010.3468	1582.95	3.95	124.060	-22.3	1.01121
0.39981	1015.3602	1597.34	3.86	125.118	-27.9	1.01316
Lysine HCl in 20% aqueous THF						
0.00000	987.8468	1584.32	4.03			
0.09871	994.3161	1592.50	3.97	116.970	-22.6	1.00482
0.19992	1000.3877	1603.45	3.89	119.102	-27.1	1.00865
0.29990	1005.9219	1615.46	3.81	120.922	-29.4	1.01171
0.39981	1010.9910	1629.28	3.73	122.701	-32.0	1.01393
Lysine HCl in 28% aqueous THF						
0.00000	981.1352	1585.41	4.05			
0.09991	989.2623	1592.04	3.99	100.824	-36.4	1.00688
0.19995	996.0716	1604.37	3.90	106.933	-37.3	1.01121
0.29991	1002.0871	1616.04	3.82	111.214	-38.1	1.01486
0.39992	1006.9768	1627.38	3.75	115.981	-39.6	1.01744

tive and negative ions are formed. The water molecules are attached to these ions by electrostatic forces thereby increasing greater cohesion in solution. The electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in the volume of solvent caused by zwitterion portion of solute is increased in aqueous solution in comparison to that of water. This implies that the system under consideration behaves like structure maker but up to a specific concentration.

The values of density and sound velocity enable to calculate the relative association, R_A (Table 1) by using the equation :

$$R_A = (d/d_0)(u_0/u)^{1/3}$$

where u_0 and u are the ultrasonic velocities of solvent and solution respectively, d_0 and d are the densities of solvent and solution respectively.

As can be seen, the value of R_A increases with increase in concentration which indicates that solvation of

lysine hydrochloride predominates over the breaking up of the solvent structure.

From the density data, the apparent molal volume (Φ_v) and the apparent molal compressibility (Φ_k) were calculated using of following equations,

$$\Phi_v = M/d - [(d - d_0)1000/mdd_0]$$

$$\Phi_k = M K_s^0/d - [(K_s^0 d - K_s d_0)/mdd_0]$$

where m is the molality, M the molecular mass of the solute and K_s^0 is the adiabatic compressibility of solvent.

The values of apparent molal volume (Φ_v) and apparent molal compressibility (Φ_k) are also summarized in Table 1. The value of apparent molal volume is positive which increases as the concentration of solute is increased.

On the other hand, the negative value of apparent molal compressibility which becomes more negative with increase in the concentration of solution can be explained in terms of loss of compressibility of surrounding solvent

molecules. According to the hypothesis of substitution dissolution⁵, the large negative values of Φ_k may also indicate the presence of packing or caging effect⁶.

According to Masson's empirical equation, Φ_v , and according to Gucker and Debye Huckel theory, Φ_k , are the linear functions of molal concentration represented as :

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v m$$

$$\Phi_k = \Phi_k^0 + S_k m$$

where Φ_v^0 is the partial molal volume at infinite dilution or limiting apparent molal volume at infinite dilution which is a measure of solute-solvent interaction and S_v is a constant. Φ_k^0 is the limiting apparent molal compressibility at infinite dilution and S_k is a constant. All these values were obtained by least square method.

Since the linear dependence of Φ_v on molality is observed for all the concentrations investigated, the limiting apparent molal volume is calculated by linear square fit of Φ_v versus molality plots. The values are reported in Table 2 for all the concentrations studied in the present work. For each concentration the positive and increasing value of apparent molal volume indicates empty space

Table 2. Values of limiting apparent molal volume, the limiting apparent molal compressibility, the constants S_v and S_k for lysine HCl at 300.56 K at different concentrations

Concn. (%)	$\Phi_v \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$S_v \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻² kg)	$\Phi_k \times 10^{15}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)	$S_k \times 10^{15}$ (m ³ mol ⁻² Pa ⁻¹ kg)
0	108.73 (±0.85) ^a	41.79 (±3.09)	-71.95 (±2.42)	62.40 (±8.85)
5	109.93 (±0.72)	40.35 (±2.64)	-9.25 (±2.53)	-49.39 (±2.60)
10	120.15 (±0.21)	12.72 (±0.78)	-7.95 (±0.75)	-48.92 (±2.74)
15	112.50 (±0.30)	20.39 (±1.08)	-9.31 (±0.19)	-51.80 (±0.69)
20	115.19 (±0.15)	18.95 (±0.55)	-20.18 (±0.93)	-30.42 (±3.41)
25	101.60 (±0.47)	51.86 (±1.72)	-11.10 (±1.07)	-57.61 (±3.92)
28	96.30 (±0.73)	49.75 (±2.67)	-35.25 (±0.30)	-10.40 (±1.10)

^aValues in the parenthesis indicate error.

around the solute molecule which depends upon physico-chemical properties of solvent being related to molecular

geometry of solute and to solute-solvent interactions. In the latter, structure making and structure breaking effect promoted by solute are included. The value of S_v for all the concentrations calculated from the slope is positive which is an indication of strong interaction.

The viscosity measurements have been analyzed in terms of Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC$$

where C is the molarity of solution, η_r ($= \eta/\eta_0$) is the relative viscosity, η_0 and η are the viscosities of solvent and solution respectively and are used to calculate viscosity B -coefficients (Table 3) using Jones-Dole equation by least square method. The value of B depends upon the size of solute and nature of solute-solvent interactions and is definite for solute-solvent system.

Table 3 shows that viscosity of solution increases with increase in concentration of solute as well as solvent. It

Table 3. Molarity, viscosity, relative viscosity and viscosity B -coefficients of Jones-Dole equation

C (mol L ⁻¹)	$\eta \times 10^{-3}$ (Pa s)	η_r	Viscosity B -coefficients (L mol ⁻¹)
Lysine HCl in aqueous solution			
0.00000	0.84525	-	0.2687
0.09848	0.86518	1.02358	
0.19470	0.88839	1.05104	
0.28844	0.91105	1.07785	
0.37960	0.93245	1.10316	
Lysine HCl in 10% aqueous THF			
0.00000	0.91996	-	0.6343
0.09808	0.98772	1.07366	
0.19389	1.03784	1.12814	
0.28727	1.08698	1.18155	
0.37832	1.13601	1.23485	
Lysine HCl in 20% aqueous THF			
0.00000	1.11995	-	0.4725
0.0964	1.15424	1.03061	
0.19295	1.20576	1.07662	
0.28601	1.27217	1.13591	
0.37670	1.33126	1.18867	
Lysine HCl in 28% aqueous THF			
0.00000	1.24578	-	0.4338
0.09707	1.29290	1.03782	
0.19215	1.34170	1.07700	
0.28493	1.39520	1.11994	
0.37530	1.45750	1.16995	

evidences the existence of molecular interactions occurring in the system which, if further analyzed, in terms of Jones-Dole coefficients gives the value of viscosity B -coefficient. The coefficient B represents measure of order or disorder introduced by solute into solution. The value of B -coefficients is positive which shows strong alignment of solvent towards solute. The strong interaction immobilizes the neighbouring solvent molecules and presents large obstruction to viscous flow of solution thereby increasing viscosity. Thus, the system lysine hydrochloride behaves as structure maker and hence is in more structured environment.

Experimental

Lysine hydrochloride, obtained from Hi Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., used in the present work was of analytical reagent having a minimum assay of 99.9%. It was recrystallised from alcohol and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride in a dessicator prior to use. Water used in the experiments was distilled thrice prior to making solutions. As a measure of the purity check, measured density of water was compared with the literature⁷. All the solutions were made by weight.

The density was measured using a 20 ml specific gravity bottle which was calibrated using triply distilled water. The specific gravity bottle containing the solutions was immersed in a constant temperature bath controlled with in ± 0.05 K by using a circular controlled temperature bath. The weighing was performed on an analytical balance (Mettler AE 240) having an accuracy of 1.0×10^{-5} g. The molalities used were in the range from 0.0 to 0.4 m while the concentration of aqueous THF was varied up to 40% in the steps of 5%. Each reported density data was an average of at least four measurements. The

uncertainty in the measured density was better than 3×10^{-5} g cm⁻³. The ultrasonic velocity in solutions was measured by determining the wavelength of sound with the help of multi frequency ultrasonic interferometer (M-82, Mittal Enterprises, India) at 4 MHz. The temperature of water surrounding the measuring cell was controlled and accuracy in the velocity measurement was $\pm 0.05\%$. The viscosity was measured with the Ostwald type viscometer using triply distilled water by using thermostatic water bath.

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